

Wisdom in animals' worlds mirrors wisdom in human life: Learn to live together

 Thi-Phuong Nguyen

Centre for Crop Systems Analysis, Wageningen University (P.O. Box 430, 6700 AK Wageningen, the Netherlands)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5047-3434>

**Note: Reviewed in the Netherlands on November 25, 2023, on Amazon. It has been lightly edited for clarity only.*

The book is a collection of story pieces about the journey of the Kingfisher, who is powerful but also lonely. I have been so impressed by the way that the main character, Kingfisher, is charted throughout the whole book. His interactions with other characters in each story carry valuable lessons in real, human life.

Beste recensie uit Nederland

Thi-Phuong Nguyen

★★★★★ **Wisdom in animals' worlds mirrors wisdom in human life: Learn to live together**

Beoordeeld in Nederland op 25 november 2023

Geverifieerde aankoop

The book is a collection of story pieces about the journey of the Kingfisher who is powerful but also lonely. I have been so impressed by the way that the main character, Kingfisher, is charted throughout the whole book. His interactions with other characters in each stories carry valuable lessons in real, human life.

Reading throughout the book, I felt like going through to be soaked in Vietnamese culture where I was born and growing up. I see the characters reflecting individuals in my small village where I spent whole 20 years of youth there. Closing the book and reading back to the author's words, I am delighted to have the same ethnic identity with him, and big thanks to him for bringing these life lessons to a forever-lasting book, which will stand there years and years. We are taught at the university and at home that, learning to know, learning to work, but the most important is learning to live together. This book reminds me of this slogan. Last but not least, reading this book took me two nights but worths over days.

Nuttig

| Overzicht

Screenshot: Amazon [1].

Reading throughout the book [1], I felt like going through to be soaked in the Vietnamese culture where I was born and growing up. I see the characters reflecting individuals in my small village where I spent the whole 20 years of youth there. Closing the book and reading back to the author's words, I am delighted to have the same ethnic identity as him, and big thanks to him for bringing these life lessons to a forever-lasting book, which will stand there for years and years. We are taught at the university and at home that, learning to know, learning to work, but the most important is learning to live together. This book reminds me of this slogan.

Last but not least, reading this book took me two nights but worth over days.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

